

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

5th TNA Call Documentation – User Report (User)

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

After the StoRIES Transnational Access stay or Virtual Access, users are required to submit a *User Report*. This should be done within 4 weeks after the Access is completed unless otherwise agreed. The *User Report* will be given to the User(s) by the Project Management. The report contains sections related to the work performed, the main results and observations that were achieved.

This document should be completed, signed, and sent to the following person, along with the *TNA Cost Claim Form* and all eligible receipts either by e-mail olga.suminska-ebersoldt@kit.edu

Summary questionnaire for users who have been granted Transnational Access (TNA) under the StoRIES project Horizon 2020 TNA scheme. More information on StoRIES TNA can be found in “[General Rules](#)” and in “[Access Policy](#)” which can be found on the StoRIES webpage.

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Development of Electrodes based on Metal Oxides for Biomass-Assisted Water Electrolysis
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	DEMO
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	Institute of Emerging Technologies, Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	biomass-assisted water electrolysis, electrodes
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	15/09/2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	16/11/2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	16/09/2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	15/11/2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	
Number of days using the RI	User ██████████ used the RI 45 days, User ██████████ used the RI 2 days on 25/09/2024 and 26/09/2024, User ██████████ used the RI 2 days on 05/11/2024 and 06/11/2024
Number of users granted access (group size)	3

Comments	
User	
User group leader or sole applicant (user group member 1)	
First name	[REDACTED]
Last name	[REDACTED]
Affiliation / Employer	ENEA - National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
Country of Employer	Italy
E-mail	[REDACTED]
Comments	
User group member 2	
First name	[REDACTED]
Last name	[REDACTED]
Affiliation / Employer	Unibas – Università degli studi della Basilicata
Country of Employer	Italy
E-mail	[REDACTED]
Comments	
User group member 3	
First name	[REDACTED]
Last name	[REDACTED]
Affiliation / Employer	ENEA - National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
Country of Employer	Italy
E-mail	[REDACTED]
Comments	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
Please insert more fields if your groups had more than four members.	

Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results

Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)

Our research objective is to develop hybrid electrodes for biomass-assisted water electrolysis, combining carbon materials and metal oxides. We aim to capitalize on the conductivity of carbon and the catalytic properties of metal oxides to enhance hydrogen production efficiency.

Specifically, our proposal focuses on synthesizing highly dispersed metal oxides (NiO, MnO₂) on highly conductive carbon substrates (e.g.: graphene oxide) to create hybrid electrodes. These electrodes will be tested to determine their optimal working potential window for hydrogen production.

Our expected outcomes include improving hydrogen production efficiency, lifespan and advancing fundamental knowledge on the electrodes and materials that can be used in this context.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

We conducted a literature review to identify suitable electrodes for the oxidation of small organic molecules, such as those present in the gasification residue of lignocellulosic biomass (e.g., catechols). The findings indicated that nickel and manganese oxide-based electrodes could be viable options due to their cost-effectiveness and promising electrochemical properties. Typically, noble and expensive metals like platinum and iridium are used for biomass oxidation and the oxidation of their gasification residues.

To this end, we synthesized nickel and manganese oxides using a hydrothermal synthesis approach, chosen for its economic viability, sustainability, and because existing literature provided a solid starting point.

The main activities involved preparing various solutions with salts as sources of manganese and nickel. A strong base or acid was then added for pH adjustment, and the solutions were left in an oven for 24 hours at 95°C. The effect of counter ions from the bases and acids used was also evaluated.

The synthesized powders were washed by filtration or centrifugation, then annealed at high temperatures (400°C for nickel and 550°C for manganese) for 3 hours in the case of nickel and 4 hours for manganese.

The obtained oxide powders were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to ensure that the crystalline phases matched the expected structures. Spectra were compared against online databases and commercial references for manganese and nickel oxides, which were measured using our instruments.

Additionally, we synthesized graphene oxide using a modified Hummer's method and subsequently electrodeposited it onto a copper substrate via chronopotentiometry, where it served as a buffer layer. Following this, we electrodeposited the hydrothermally synthesized nickel and manganese oxides onto two distinct substrates: copper and graphene oxide, also using chronopotentiometry.

We devoted a significant amount of time to optimizing experimental parameters to ensure reproducibility of results and the best yields from the synthesis. Preliminary experiments assessed the effect of synthesis conditions (temperature, reaction time, pH) on the crystallinity and morphology of the metal oxides. Systematic variations of these parameters were conducted to identify ideal conditions for obtaining highly dispersed and stable oxides. Similar studies were performed to optimize annealing times and temperatures and to determine the most time-efficient procedures overall.

Furthermore, we conducted studies on the electrochemical stability of the synthesized materials, monitoring changes in their properties over time through repeated cyclic voltammetry tests. These

tests were critical for understanding the behavior of the materials under prolonged usage conditions, simulating realistic application scenarios.

The entire process was meticulously documented, creating a knowledge base that will be beneficial for future experiments.

Electrochemical experiments were performed using an Autolab potentiostat, while XRD spectra were recorded with a Rigaku diffractometer. Surface morphology and microstructural analyses of the synthesized powders were conducted using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM), the JEOL JSM-IT700HR.

The entire synthesis and fabrication process adhered to green chemistry principles, minimizing waste and reliance on hazardous chemicals, making the process both environmentally friendly and scalable for industrial applications.

References:

<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.1c04223>

<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jp8052967>

<https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0000228>

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2021.161012>

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Our study focused on developing hybrid electrodes combining carbon materials and metal oxides to enhance hydrogen production efficiency via biomass-assisted water electrolysis. The experiments were conducted at the Institute of Emerging Technologies, Hellenic Mediterranean University (HMU), leveraging their advanced facilities for material synthesis and characterization. Nickel and manganese oxides were synthesized using a hydrothermal method to ensure economic feasibility and environmental sustainability. These materials were selected based on their affordability and promising electrochemical properties for the oxidation of small organic molecules present in biomass gasification residues. Graphene oxide (GO) was synthesized using the modified Hummer's method. This material was electrodeposited onto copper substrates via chronopotentiometry, creating a conductive buffer layer for electrode fabrication.

Structural and morphological analyses confirmed the successful synthesis and desired properties of these materials. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses validated the crystallinity of nickel and manganese oxides, while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) provided detailed insights into their microstructural characteristics. In particular we synthesized MnO₂ nanoparticles with crystal sizes of about 50 nm in α and δ phases. The crystallinity for NiO nanoparticles was less remarkable. Nickel and manganese oxides were electrodeposited onto copper and graphene oxide substrates using chronopotentiometry. This approach ensured robust and uniform deposition, essential for maintaining the electrodes' performance and stability during electrochemical tests. The hybrid structure, combining the high conductivity of graphene oxide with the catalytic activity of metal oxides, demonstrated improved electrochemical properties.

The entire synthesis and fabrication process adhered to principles of green chemistry, minimizing waste and reliance on hazardous chemicals. This not only makes the process environmentally friendly but also scalable for industrial applications.

The successful development of these hybrid electrodes opens avenues for further exploration in biomass valorisation and energy storage. The adaptability of the synthesis process allows for customization of electrode properties for various applications. Also, the hybrid electrode approach could potentially be adapted for other oxidation reactions, expanding its utility in electrochemical systems.

Overall, the work on the project until now aim to demonstrates the effectiveness of combining advanced material science with practical applications to address pressing energy challenges.

Further studies will focus on optimizing the electrode design and integrating the system into laboratory-scale water electrolysis units for real-world applications.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

This study focused on developing and evaluating electrodes suitable for the oxidation of small organic molecules, such as catechol, derived from the gasification residues of lignocellulosic biomass. A literature review highlighted nickel and manganese oxide-based electrodes as promising candidates due to their affordability and favorable electrochemical properties.

Using a hydrothermal synthesis approach, we successfully synthesized nickel and manganese oxides, which were characterized through X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) JEOL JSM-IT700HR to confirm their crystalline structure and morphology. In parallel, graphene oxide was prepared via a modified Hummer's method and deposited onto copper substrates by chronopotentiometry, serving as a buffer layer for subsequent electrode fabrication. Nickel and manganese oxides were then electrodeposited onto both copper and graphene oxide substrates using the same electrochemical method.

The electrochemical performance of these hybrid electrodes was investigated using an Autolab potentiostat, while their structural and morphological features were analyzed with XRD diffractometer and field-emission SEM. These analyses confirmed the successful fabrication of hybrid electrodes with desired properties.

The results demonstrate that green, cost-effective, and sustainable methods can be employed to synthesize nickel and manganese oxide powders and fabricate hybrid electrodes. The combination of nickel or manganese oxides with graphene oxide enhances the electrodes' potential for the low-energy oxidation of the small organic molecules of our substrates. Importantly, the integration of this oxidation process with water electrolysis offers a dual benefit: the valorization of organic residues and the generation of pure hydrogen at the cathode with reduced energy consumption. These findings underline the potential of these hybrid electrodes to contribute to sustainable energy solutions, leveraging biomass-derived residues for hydrogen production while minimizing waste.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

We have achieved, through green, cost-effective, and sustainable methods, the synthesis of nickel and manganese oxide powders using hydrothermal techniques, and graphene oxide using a modified Hummer's method. Additionally, we employed electrochemical approaches such as electrodeposition via chronopotentiometry to produce hybrid electrodes. These electrodes are designed to be optimal for the low-potential oxidation of organic molecules like catechols, which are commonly found in the gasification residues of plant biomass. The combined oxidation process, integrated with water electrolysis, is expected to enable the generation of pure hydrogen at the cathode with low energy consumption.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Intended publications

Conferences in biomass/bioeconomy/biorefinery such as the EUBCE 2025. Publications in Scientific int. journals like Int. Journal of Hydrogen Energy (Elsevier ed.), Processes (MDPI ed.).

Data management

The experimental data and worked outputs will be stored as Excel, Word, PDF, JPEG files, by ENEA and HMU both. The data will be made available by open access publication, including their upload as supplementary file, if useful.

Conclusions / additional comments					
The work will be continued and expanded in ENEA facilities by testing the fabricated electrodes with real samples of gasification residuals from lignocellulosic biomass for improving biomass-assisted water electrolysis. The collaboration between the Users and the RI Host will continue.					
Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	

Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

I have read the [StoRIES privacy policy](#) for participation in the StoRIES TNA and consent to participation and the associated data processing.

Date of submission to StoRIES TNA team:

Yo
Yo

A large black rectangular box redacting the date of submission. The text "Yo" is visible on the left side of the box, appearing to be the start of the words "Year" and "Month".